

and MTU6024 (Laxmi) seedlings were planted to see if the inoculum was from the nursery or other sources.

No ShB infection was noticed until 52 DT, when most cultures showed symptoms (see table). Other cultures showed infection at 66 and 76 DT. Infection gradually increased for all cultures after 52 DT. At 100 DT some susceptible cultures showed almost 100% infection. The healthy MTU7029 and MTU6024 seedlings also developed infection, indicating that the inoculum might have been from a source other than the nursery. Late appearance of ShB symptoms (52 DT) also may indicate that carry-over of inoculum from nursery to adult plants is a remote possibility. □

Sheath blight infection carry-over from nursery to adult plants.

Culture	Hills observed (no.)	Sheath blight-infected hills (no.) at indicated time				
		52 DT	66 DT	76 DT	86 DT	100 DT
<i>Infected</i>						
MTU7029	152	24	67	131	140	150
MTU8002	152	1	24	59	86	88
MTU7633	152	15	41	79	96	142
MTU7030	152	4	25	58	100	147
MTU2281	152	3	18	60	96	145
MTU2292	152	1	1	14	38	74
MTU2066	80	1	8	25	36	36
MTU2194	152	0	2	5	25	81
MTU4865	114	0	0	5	26	76
MTU6117	76	0	0	10	26	50
MTU6613	152	8	43	93	125	152
IET6919	152	2	4	14	80	81
IET7235	152	2	4	8	25	51
<i>Healthy</i>						
MTU7029	152	25	69	120	130	152
MTU6024	152	20	60	115	128	150

Blast outbreak in Manipur

D. K. Gupta, Plant Pathology Department, ICAR Research Complex for N.E.H. Region, Manipur Centre, Babupara, Imphal 795001, Manipur, India

Blast (Bl) caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* is the most important rice disease in the northeastern hill region of India. In Manipur, Bl severely damages crops when the weather is favorable. In 1982 kharif, Bl affected all the high yielding varieties (IR24, Pusa 33, and Punshi). Punshi was most damaged (Table 1).

Table 1. Neck blast in 5 varieties at Lamphalpat farm, Manipur.

Year	Neck blast (%)				
	Pusa 33	Punshi	IR24	Prasad	RCM2
1981	84.8	100	18.2	0.7	0
1982	36.9	98.9	15.0	0.7	11.9

We surveyed fields in 5 subdivisions (50 hills/field and 2 fields/subdivision, selected randomly). Percent neck Bl incidence was highest in Moidangpok and lowest in Sawombung (Table 2). □

Table 2. Neck blast incidence in Punshi during 1982 kharif in Central district, Manipur.

Subdivision	Village	Neck blast (%)
Thoubal	Thoubal	48.2
	Haothamamana	28.4
	Kakching	18.0
Bishenpur	Bishenpur	17.7
	Ningthoukhong	28.9
	Toubul	71.0
Imphal West I	Khumbong	85.0
	Moidangpok	100.0
Imphal West II	Lamphalpat	98.9
	Ningombam	84.0
	Wangoi	30.0
Imphal East	Sawombung	15.0
	Pungdongbam	18.0
Av		49.5

Occurrence of rice yellow dwarf disease in Patna (Bihar) India

S. K. Singh (present address: Station de Pathologie Végétale, Centre National de la Recherche Agronomique, Route de Saint Cyr – 78000 Versailles, France), Plant Pathology Department, Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack – 753006 Orissa; and R. C. Chaudhary, Rajendra Agricultural University, Agricultural Research Institute (ARI), Mithapur, Patna, Bihar, India

Rice yellow dwarf disease was discovered on ratooned Sita plants at the ARI Farm in Mithapur, Nov 1982. Infected plants were chlorotic with pronounced stunting and profuse tillering. Chlorotic leaves were a uniform pale yellow. Isolated patches of infected hills were observed in

the field. IET5852 rice plants and stubble in adjoining plots were disease free.

A disease transmission test of suspected diseased plants from the field was conducted with second-instar nymphs of *Nephotettix virescens* (Distant). Nymphs were allowed to feed on test samples for 48 h and were incubated 25 days before 48 h of inoculation feeding on 10-day-old healthy TN1 seedlings. Yellow dwarf symptoms developed in about a month, confirming the disease.

This report confirms the presence of yellow dwarf disease in Patna Bihar as was first reported in 1967. Further spread of the disease should be monitored, diseased plants should be removed from fields and destroyed, and resistant varieties should be planted. □

Purification and serological properties of rice grassy stunt virus 2

H. Hibino and P. Q. Cabauatan, IRRI; and T. Omura and T. Tsuchizaki, Institute for Plant Virus Research, Tsukuba, Ibaraki, 305 Japan

Rice grassy stunt virus 2 (RGSV 2), a strain of rice grassy stunt virus (RGSV 1), was purified following the procedure for grassy stunt virus in Japan. The sap of infected plants was clarified with magnesium bentonite and carbon tetrachloride (CCl₄), treated with polyethylene glycol (PEG), and centrifuged in 10-45% sucrose density gradient. Electron microscopy of the purified fraction revealed numerous filamentous particles of various